

MYC directly transactivates CR2/CD21, the receptor of the Epstein-Barr virus, enhancing the viral infection of Burkitt lymphoma cells

Ester Molina^{1,6,7}, Lucía García-Gutiérrez^{1,7}, Vanessa Junco¹, Mercedes Perez-Olivares², Virginia G. de Yébenes^{3,4}, Rosa Blanco¹, Laura Quevedo¹, Juan C Acosta¹, Ana V. Marín⁴, Daniela Ulgiati⁵, Ramon Merino¹, M. Dolores Delgado¹, Ignacio Varela¹, José R. Regueiro⁴, Ignacio Moreno de Alborán², Almudena R. Ramiro³ and Javier León¹ *

¹Instituto de Biomedicina y Biotecnología de Cantabria (IBBTEC), Universidad de Cantabria-CSIC, and Departamento de Biología Molecular, Universidad de Cantabria, Santander, Spain.

²Department of Immunology and Oncology, Centro Nacional de Biotecnología (CNB)-CSIC, Madrid, Spain.

³Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Cardiovasculares-CNIC Carlos III, Madrid, Spain

⁴Department of Immunology, Ophthalmology and ENT, Universidad Complutense, School of Medicine and 12 de Octubre Health Research Institute (imas12), Madrid, Spain.

⁵School of Biomedical Sciences, The University of Western Australia, Crawley, WA, Australia

⁶Present address: Hormel Institute, University of Minnesota, USA

⁷These authors contributed equally

*Corresponding author

ABSTRACT

MYC is an oncogenic transcription factor dysregulated in about half of total human tumors. While transcriptomic studies reveal more than 1000 genes regulated by MYC, a much smaller fraction of genes is directly transactivated by MYC. Virtually all Burkitt lymphoma (BL) carry chromosomal translocations involving MYC oncogene. Most endemic BL and a fraction of sporadic BL are associated to Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection. The currently accepted mechanism is that EBV is the BL causing agent inducing MYC translocation. Herein we show that the EBV receptor, *CR2* (also called *CD21*), is a direct MYC target gene. This is based on several evidences: MYC induces *CR2* expression in both proliferating and arrested cells and in the absence of protein synthesis, binds the *CR2* promoter and transactivates *CR2* in an E-box dependent manner. Moreover, using mice with conditional MYC ablation we show that MYC induces *CR2* in primary B cells. Importantly, modulation of MYC levels directly correlates with EBV's ability of infection in BL cells. Altogether, in contrast to the widely accepted hypothesis for the correlation between EBV and BL, we propose an alternative hypothesis in which MYC dysregulation could be a first event leading to the subsequent EBV infection.

Introduction

2 MYC is a transcription factor that belongs to the b-HLH-LZ family of proteins and binds DNA as a
3 dimer with MAX. MYC-MAX heterodimers bind to the DNA to consensus sequences called E-
4 boxes (CANNTG motif), present in most MYC target genes [1, 2]. MYC transforms cells
5 modulating functions essential in tumor cell biology as cell cycle progression, energetic
6 metabolism, lipid and nucleotide biosynthesis, protein synthesis, apoptosis and differentiation [1-
7 3]. MYC regulates more than one thousand genes [4-7]. However, the identification of direct MYC
8 target genes is hampered because MYC is a weak transactivator but provokes profound changes
9 in cell physiology. Therefore, many of these genes are regulated not directly by MYC but as a
10 secondary effect of changes induced by MYC. Indeed, only a minority of the genes having MYC
11 bound at the promoter are identified as direct MYC targets (reviewed in [8]).

12 MYC is dysregulated in about 50% of human malignancies of different types [9, 10] and
13 it is particularly prevalent in lymphoma and leukemia [11, 12]. Burkitt lymphoma (BL) is an
14 aggressive lymphoma originally described in equatorial Africa [13]. It is the most common
15 childhood cancer in areas where malaria is endemic in Africa, Brazil and Papua New Guinea.
16 This BL variant is called endemic BL (eBL) and shows high prevalence in children (5-10 per 10⁵
17 cases/year). Clinically and histologically similar BL occurs in Europe and USA affecting children
18 and adults with much lesser prevalence, a variant called sporadic BL (sBL). A third less common
19 variant is the immunodeficiency-associated BL [14, 15].

20 BL is believed to originate in the germinal center of lymph nodes, where rapidly dividing
21 B cells undergo somatic hypermutation and class-switch recombination of the immunoglobulin
22 genes. MYC plays a prominent role in germinal center formation [12, 16]. Activation-induced
23 cytidine deaminase (AID) initiates somatic hypermutation and class switch recombination [17],
24 but it can also induce Ig/MYC translocations [18, 19]. MYC is translocated to one of the
25 immunoglobulin *loci* in nearly all BL cases, resulting in aberrant MYC expression under the control
26 of the immunoglobulin enhancers. The most frequent translocation occurs into the
27 immunoglobulin heavy chain [t(8;14)(q24;q32)] but it could also be found in the light chain *loci*.
28 Besides MYC translocations, 30-50% of BL carry mutations within the MYC gene [15, 20, 21],
29 many of them generating a more stable MYC protein [22].

30 The Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) is a herpesvirus originally discovered associated to endemic
31 BL. The global prevalence of EBV in BL patients is around 50% and it is decreasing over the last
32 20 years. However, while EBV is present in more than 90% of the endemic BL cases, it is detected
33 in only 1-2% of adults and 30-40% of children with sporadic BL. EBV is also detected in 30-40%
34 of patients with the immunodeficiency-associated BL [14, 23, 24]. EBV establishes a harmless
35 lifelong infection in B cells in over 95% of adults worldwide, and it is associated to infectious
36 mononucleosis [25] and multiple sclerosis [26, 27]. EBV was the first virus described with
37 oncogenic potential due to its association with BL and its ability to transform B cells into
38 immortalized lymphoblastoid cell lines [28]. EBV can display three gene expression programs,
39 called latency programs I, II and III, in which different sets of viral genes are expressed [23, 26,

40 28]. These genes are involved in processes leading to B cell transformation, such as
41 immortalization [29], resistance to apoptosis [30] and metabolic reprogramming [31].

42 The most accepted hypothesis to explain the high incidence of EBV in endemic BL
43 proposes a causative role for EBV. This hypothesis stemmed from the finding of high EBV
44 antibodies titers in sera of African children before the BL diagnosis [32]. This and subsequent
45 reports led to the declaration of EBV as a causative agent of BL by the WHO [33]. EBV, malaria
46 and HIV infection are cofactors that may cooperate with MYC in promoting B cell proliferation in
47 the germinal center by reducing apoptosis or impairing the immune-surveillance of the tumor [14,
48 34, 35]. However, the pathogenic mechanism by which EBV genes promote MYC translocation
49 in BL tumorigenesis is unclear. Furthermore, some data do not fit with the hypothesis of EBV
50 being the cause of BL. EBV infection is absent in the vast majority of the adult sporadic BL cases,
51 while EBV infection is associated to other tumors (e.g., nasopharyngeal carcinoma, gastric
52 cancer, Hodgkin lymphoma, post-transplant lymphoproliferative disease, peripheral T cell
53 lymphoma) where MYC translocation is absent (reviewed in [23, 26, 36]). EBV infects B
54 lymphocytes through a membrane glycoprotein, the complement receptor 2 or CR2 (also termed
55 CD21) [37]. CR2 acts as a co-receptor for B Cell Receptor (BCR) and is found in a complex with
56 other proteins such as CD19 or CD81 [38].

57 In this work, we show that MYC directly induces CR2 expression in BL-derived cell lines
58 and primary B cells. Induction of CR2 by MYC overexpression leads to higher number of EBV-
59 infected cells. Based on this, we propose an alternative mechanism in which the upregulation of
60 MYC due to chromosomal translocation increases the receptor density at the B cell surface,
61 leading to B-lymphocytes more prone to infection by EBV.

62
63

64 **Results**

65 **MYC downregulation leads to decreased CR2 expression in lymphoma cells.**

66 Previous studies on gene expression profiling of K562 leukemia cells revealed *CR2* as
67 one of the genes regulated by MYC (J.C. Acosta, PhD Thesis Dissertation, University of
68 Cantabria, 2005). Given the involvement of MYC in BL, we investigated whether *CR2* could be a
69 novel MYC target gene. Treatment of Raji cells (BL cell line) and Jurkat cells (acute T cell
70 lymphoblastic leukemia cell line) with JQ1, an inhibitor of the bromodomain and extra terminal
71 (BET) family of proteins known to potently inhibit MYC transcription [39], resulted in MYC mRNA
72 down-regulation. This was accompanied with a decrease in *CR2* mRNA expression (Fig. 1A). The
73 decrease in MYC and CR2 expression was also detected at the protein level in both cell lines
74 (Fig. 1B). MYC is necessary to maintain cell cycle progression and MYC downregulation is known
75 to arrest proliferation [3]. In agreement, the treatment of Raji and Jurkat cells with increasing
76 concentrations of JQ1 decreased their proliferative capacity in a dose-dependent manner
77 (Supplementary Fig. 1A) and increased the percentage of cells in G₁ phase (Supplementary Fig.
78 1B). Longer exposure to JQ1 resulted in apoptosis, as shown by annexin V staining
79 (Supplementary Fig. 1C).

80 To investigate a direct effect of MYC downregulation on *CR2* expression, we asked
81 whether *MYC* silencing led to *CR2* downregulation. We knocked down *MYC* expression in Raji
82 cells using short-hairpin RNA constructs (shMYC)-containing lentiviral particles (a mixture of two
83 sh constructs targeting human *MYC*). The results showed that *MYC* depletion significantly
84 reduced *CR2* mRNA and protein levels (Fig. 1C). The rate of cell proliferation was also
85 dramatically reduced upon *MYC* silencing (Fig. 1D).

86 It is reported that high *MYC* levels inhibit the induction of EBV lytic cycle in BL cells [40].
87 Thus, we asked whether *MYC* silencing in our Raji cells model can induce EBV lytic cycle. We
88 silenced *MYC* expression with shMYC lentivirus and determined the expression of viral genes
89 associated to the lytic cycle. The results showed that *MYC* knockdown resulted in the induction
90 of early-lytic genes as *BZLF1*, *BLLF1* and *BRLF1*. (Supplementary Fig. 2). As a positive control
91 we used 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate (TPA), reported to induce lytic genes in Raji cells
92 [41].

93

94 **MYC upregulates *CR2* mRNA expression independently of cell proliferation.**

95 The former results can be explained if *CR2* expression is linked to the proliferation state
96 of the cell, so it would decrease as a consequence of proliferation arrest in *MYC*-depleted cells.
97 To address this issue, we used KMyCJ cells, a K562 derived cell line with ectopic *MYC* expression
98 inducible by Zn^{2+} addition [42]. In these cells, JQ1 treatment decreased endogenous *MYC*
99 expression while the addition of Zn^{2+} induced the exogenous *MYC* (Fig. 2A,C). Total *MYC* levels
100 did not increase in growing cells treated with Zn^{2+} likely due to a well-known *MYC* auto
101 suppression mechanism by which exogenous *MYC* downregulates endogenous *MYC* levels in
102 most systems, so that total *MYC* levels do not raise above a certain threshold [43, 44]. The
103 proliferative arrest of KMyCJ cells upon JQ1 treatment was not rescued by ectopic *MYC*
104 expression (Fig. 2B). We found that induction of *MYC* by Zn^{2+} resulted in the upregulation of *CR2*
105 mRNA levels in JQ1-arrested cells (Fig. 2C). To further confirm that *CR2* regulation by *MYC* is
106 independent from the proliferative state of the cells, we performed a similar experiment but
107 inducing cell cycle arrest with TPA, a drug known to arrest proliferation and dramatically reduce
108 *MYC* levels in these cells [44]. KMyCJ cells were treated with TPA and then the ectopic *MYC*
109 expression was induced with Zn^{2+} . As shown in Fig. 2D, TPA induced a proliferative arrest that
110 was not rescued by *MYC* upon Zn^{2+} addition. We found that *CR2* mRNA levels increased upon
111 *MYC* induction even in TPA-arrested cells (Fig. 2E).

112 As a parallel approach, we used another K562 derived cell line, Kp27MER, which
113 contains a *CDKN1B* transgene ($p27^{KIP}$) inducible by Zn^{2+} and the chimeric protein *MYC-ER* which
114 becomes activated by 4-hydroxy-tamoxifen (4HT). $p27^{KIP}$ is a CDK and cell cycle inhibitor and as
115 expected, addition of Zn^{2+} induced $p27$ expression and inhibited cell proliferation (Fig. 2F).
116 Despite this proliferation arrest, we observed an increase in *CR2* expression after *MYC-ER*
117 activation (Fig. 2G). As a control we confirmed the *MYC*-dependent upregulation of *LDHA*, a *bona*
118 *fade* *MYC* target gene [45]. Taken together, the results suggest that *CR2* induction is an effect of
119 *MYC* and not a consequence of *MYC*-mediated proliferation.

120

121 MYC directly binds to the CR2 promoter.

122 Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP)-seq data generated by the ENCODE Consortium
123 (<https://genome-euro.ucsc.edu>, GRCh37/hg19) predicted two peaks of MYC and MAX occupancy
124 within the proximal region of CR2 promoter in human B cells (Fig. 3A). There are four canonical
125 E-boxes in the region surrounding the CR2 transcription start site (TSS), two of which mapped
126 within the promoter near the TSS and the other two within the first intron (Fig. 3B). To confirm
127 MYC binding to CR2 promoter in BL derived cells we performed ChIP with an anti-MYC antibody
128 in Raji cells, analyzing different regions of the CR2 promoter and first intron. The results showed
129 an enrichment of MYC binding to the proximal region of CR2 promoter in a region containing two
130 close E-boxes in a region 40 bp upstream the TSS of CR2 (Fig. 3C). This is consistent with the
131 hypothesis that MYC is a regulator of CR2 transcription. To validate the MYC-dependent
132 transactivation of CR2 we performed luciferase assays with a luciferase reporter under the control
133 of the CR2 promoter region harboring the two E-boxes located ~200 bp upstream the TSS. The
134 reporter was transfected along with a short-hairpin MYC construct. The results showed that
135 knocking down MYC expression leads to a dramatic drop of the CR2 promoter activity (Fig. 3D).
136 To assess the relevance of the E-boxes for MYC transactivation we carried out ChIP assays on
137 two reporter constructs containing deletions in either E-box 1 or E-box 2. The results showed that
138 the lack of any of the two E-boxes significantly decreased MYC occupancy (Fig. 3E). We conclude
139 that MYC binds CR2 promoter and stimulates its transcription in an E-box-dependent manner.

140

**141 MYC-ER activation upregulates CR2 expression in the absence of de novo protein
142 synthesis.**

143 Our results showed that MYC induces CR2 expression independently on MYC-mediated
144 effects on proliferation. However, these results do not rule out the possibility that another MYC-
145 target gene encoding for a different transcription factor being the responsible for CR2 up-
146 regulation. To test whether CR2 is a direct MYC target, we took advantage of a K562 derived cell
147 line expressing a conditional MYC-Estrogen Receptor chimeric protein (KMER4 cells) which is
148 activatable by 4HT [42]. We asked whether MYC was capable of inducing CR2 expression in the
149 absence of *de novo* protein synthesis. We treated KMER4 cells with cycloheximide, a protein
150 synthesis inhibitor, and 4HT. This approach would discriminate between a direct MYC
151 transcriptional effect on CR2 promoter from an indirect mechanism (Fig. 4A). Endogenous MYC
152 protein levels dramatically decreased after 6 h of cycloheximide treatment, as expected, while
153 MYC-ER was detectable in cells treated with 4HT and cycloheximide (Fig. 4B). Treatment with
154 4HT, which activated MYC-ER, increased CR2 mRNA levels even in cycloheximide-treated cells,
155 where new proteins cannot be synthesized. This result rules out the possibility of an intermediate
156 MYC-target gene activating CR2 expression (Fig. 4C). Taken together, the data show that MYC
157 directly activates CR2 transcription.

158 Interestingly, CR2 interacts with the BCR complex [46] and is required for optimal B cell
159 proliferation [47, 48]. Thus, we asked whether MYC-mediated upregulation of CR2 could also

160 contribute to B cell proliferation in our model system. To explore this, we silenced *CR2* through
161 lentivirus expressing two short-hairpin constructs in Raji cells (Supplementary Fig. 3A) and
162 assayed the effect of CR2 depletion on proliferation. The results showed that *CR2* knockdown
163 produced a dramatic decrease in the proliferation of Raji cells (Supplementary Fig. 3B).

164

165 **MYC induces *CR2* expression in primary B cells**

166 To address whether MYC induces *CR2* expression also in primary B cells, we analyzed
167 by flow cytometry the expression of MYC and *CR2* in splenic B lymphocytes from C57/BL6 wild
168 type mice. We found that the fraction of cells with 10% higher MYC expression levels also showed
169 higher *CR2* expression (Fig. 5A), thus confirming the correlation observed in human cell lines. A
170 correlation between MYC and *CR2* mRNA levels can also be found in hematopoietic human
171 tissues (GEPIA, <http://gepia.cancer-pku.cn/>) (Supplementary Fig. 4). To confirm this correlation
172 we analyzed *Cr2* expression in mice where *Myc* can be conditionally depleted in primary B
173 lymphocytes in the *Myc^{fl/fl};Max^{fl/+};Cd19^{cre/+};Rosa26^{gfp/gfp}* (MycKO-Cd19) model previously
174 described by us [49]. This mouse carries one allele of *Max* and both alleles of *Myc* flanked by *loxP*
175 sites. Expression of *Cre* recombinase is driven by the endogenous promoter of *Cd19* and
176 promotes specific *Myc* deletion in B lymphocytes and expression of GFP [49]. GFP allows the
177 rapid identification and analysis of B lymphocytes that have undergone deletion of *Myc*. Primary
178 B lymphocytes from the spleens of MycKO-Cd19 and heterozygous control mice were activated
179 with LPS and interleukin-4, stained with anti-Cr2/Cd21 antibody and analyzed by flow cytometry.
180 We observed a dramatic decrease in the population of Cr2/Cd21⁺ cells within the GFP⁺ population
181 (*Myc* deleted cells) in the MycKO-Cd19 compared to heterozygous control mice before and after
182 48 h of activation (Fig. 5B). To see whether this effect was specific for *Cr2/Cd21*, we analyzed
183 the surface expression of the activation marker CD69 on the same cells. We did not see any
184 significant differences of CD69 surface expression between mutant and control cells
185 (Supplementary Fig. 5). To confirm the induction of *Cr2* by *Myc*, we overexpressed MYC in
186 primary mouse splenic B cells by retroviral transduction with MYC, encoded in an Orange-reporter
187 bicistronic IRES vector (Fig. 5C), as well as with control Orange retrovirus. We found that MYC-
188 transduced cells expressed higher *Cr2* levels (Fig. 5C). In light of these data, we conclude that
189 MYC promotes *CR2* expression not only in human cell lines but also in murine primary B cells.

190

191 **MYC depletion decreases and MYC expression enhances EBV infection efficiency**

192 Our results indicate that the EBV receptor, *CR2*, is a direct MYC target gene. Thus, we
193 wanted to elucidate whether the modulation of MYC expression correlated with the infection
194 capacity of EBV. Unlike Raji cells, Ramos is an EBV-negative BL cell line and thus a suitable
195 model to test this hypothesis, despite the low *CR2* expression in these cells. We first confirmed
196 that, in contrast to Raji cells, total genomic DNA (gDNA) of Ramos did not contain EBV sequences
197 (Fig. 6A). We then confirmed by immunoblot the downregulation of MYC protein upon shMYC
198 lentiviral infection of Ramos cells. Both shMYC lentiviral constructs were able to silence MYC in
199 Ramos cells (Fig. 6B) and we used a mix of both shMYC virus in subsequent experiments.

200 Transduction of Ramos cells with shMYC resulted in down-regulation of *MYC* and *CR2* mRNA
201 (Fig. 6C). To investigate the correlation between MYC and EBV infection, cells were transduced
202 with shMYC lentivirus, selected with puromycin and infected with EBV-containing supernatants
203 from a producer cell line (Fig. 6D). gDNA was prepared from control and MYC-depleted Ramos
204 cells and sequences of *EBNA1* and *LMP1* were measured to quantify EBV infection by qPCR.
205 Cells previously infected with shMYC lentivirus showed reduced content of EBV genes (Fig. 6E).
206 These results cannot be explained by a slower growth of MYC-silenced cells as the proliferation
207 rate of the cells did not significantly modify the extent of EBV infection (Supplementary Fig. 6).
208 We sought to confirm these results through a complementary approach, testing the infection of
209 EBV by the presence of a viral protein (gp350/250) in the cells membrane after short exposure to
210 the virus. Raji cells were used as they express higher CR2 levels than Ramos. Cells were
211 transduced with shMYC lentivirus, selected with puromycin and infected with EBV for 2.5 h (Fig.
212 6F). Silencing of MYC was assessed by RT-qPCR (Fig. 6G). The quantification of the
213 immunofluorescence analyses showed that in cells with lower MYC expression, the level of EBV
214 infection dropped significantly (Fig. 6H). As JQ1 down-regulates MYC in Raji cells (Fig. 1), we
215 also tested the extent of EBV infection in cells treated with JQ1. The result showed a dramatic
216 decrease in the fraction of EBV-infected cells as assessed by immunofluorescence
217 (Supplementary Fig. 7). The decrease of MYC at the protein was also confirmed by double
218 immunofluorescence in cells either transduced with shMYC lentivirus or treated with JQ1
219 (Supplementary Figure 8).

220 In a second experimental approach we overexpressed MYC by transducing Ramos cells
221 with a lentiviral vector that expressed MYC (LvMYC). Three days after lentiviral infection and
222 puromycin selection, cells were infected with EBV for further 48 h (Fig. 7A). The protein levels of
223 MYC in transduced cells was confirmed by immunoblot (Fig. 7B). Total gDNA was prepared and
224 the levels of EBNA1 and LMP1 DNA were analyzed by qPCR. The results showed an increased
225 infection in cells expressing higher MYC levels (Fig. 7C). Altogether, the results indicate that EBV
226 infection is enhanced by high MYC levels.

227

228

229 Discussion

230 In this work we propose a new mechanism for the pathogenesis of Burkitt lymphoma, based on
231 the MYC-mediated induction of CR2, the Epstein-Barr virus receptor. We found a *CR2* down-
232 regulation in B and T cell lines (Raji and Jurkat cell lines respectively) treated with the drug JQ1,
233 described as a potent inhibitor of MYC expression, and with short hairpin (sh) constructs of MYC.
234 These results, together with our initial observation in K562 cells, confirmed that MYC regulates
235 *CR2* expression, a result also observed in transcriptomic studies in different cell lines including B
236 cells [6, 50, 51]. Both JQ1 and shMYC caused proliferation arrest, mediated by low MYC levels.
237 Therefore, it was conceivable that *CR2* downregulation could be a consequence of the

238 proliferation arrest instead of being directly transactivated by MYC. The same effect may apply to
239 other MYC regulated genes revealed in transcriptomic studies. To analyze MYC-mediated
240 induction of CR2 in the absence of cell proliferation we used cells engineered with inducible MYC
241 alleles and observed *CR2* up-regulation in response to MYC expression in arrested cells upon
242 JQ1 treatment. Noteworthy, JQ1 and other BET inhibitors are currently being tested in clinical
243 trials in B cell malignancies primarily due to their effect on MYC expression [39]. However, our
244 results show that ectopic MYC expression fails to rescue the anti-proliferative effect of JQ1,
245 suggesting that the anti-tumoral effect of the BRD4 inhibitor is not only dependent on MYC
246 repression. Additionally, we used two other experimental approaches in which MYC activity can
247 be induced upon arrested proliferation i.e. by TPA treatment and by p27 enforced expression.
248 Both proved that MYC-dependent *CR2* induction is not a consequence of the MYC-induced
249 proliferation but a direct effect of MYC. These studies were performed in human cell lines,
250 however, using mice with a *Myc*-conditional knock-out allele and mouse primary B cells
251 transduced with MYC we showed that MYC-mediated upregulation of *Cr2* gene in murine primary
252 B cells.

253 These results showed that *CR2* upregulation after MYC overexpression (and *CR2*
254 downregulation after MYC depletion) is independent of the proliferative state of the cells,
255 consistently with *CR2* being a direct MYC target gene. To further confirm this, we performed (i)
256 ChIP experiments showing MYC binding close to the human *CR2* transcription start site, which
257 required the presence of two E-boxes and (ii) luciferase reporter assays showing that MYC
258 activated the *CR2* promoter. These results suggested that *CR2* is a MYC direct target gene.
259 Nonetheless, two facts must be noted: first, binding to chromatin does not mean that a gene is
260 actually transactivated by a transcription factor, and second, that there are many transcription
261 factors that are themselves MYC target genes. Thus, it is possible that MYC induces other
262 transcription factor(s) which in turn induces *CR2*. However, we ruled out this possibility as MYC
263 was able to activate *CR2* transcription in the absence of *de novo* protein synthesis. Thus, we
264 conclude that *CR2* is a direct MYC target gene. The analysis of the expression data from 60 BL
265 available in public databases shows that there is not a tight correlation between MYC and *CR2*
266 levels, although MYC missense mutations are significantly more frequent in lymphomas with
267 higher *CR2* expression (cBioPortal, <http://cbioportal.org>) [52]. It is possible that *CR2* upregulation
268 by MYC occurs at the first stages of cell transformation into BL cell and is not maintained through
269 subsequent advanced stages. It must be also noted that MYC expression is already high in the
270 advanced lymphomas included in these transcriptomic studies, so a lack of correlation would not
271 be surprising since there are no low MYC expressing samples to compare with. Finally, there are
272 other transcription factors known to regulate *CR2* expression acting on the promoter (e.g. AP1,
273 USF1, SP1, NFκB and NOTCH1) that may operate in advanced but not early tumor stages [53-
274 56], two of them (NOTCH1 and NFκB) reported to be positive regulators of MYC transcription in
275 lymphoid cells [57, 58].

276 The relationship between EBV infection and MYC translocation events in BL is a matter
277 of debate as the mechanism whereby EBV leads to MYC dysregulation remains ill-defined. The

278 most accepted hypothesis proposes that EBV infection would lead to the activation and expansion
279 of germinal center B cells and subsequent MYC translocation (schematized in Fig. 8). Indeed, the
280 correlation between high EBV antibody titers and BL found in African children led to declare EBV
281 as the causative agent of BL [33]. However, other evidences argue against this “virus first” model.
282 First, in most sporadic BL cases EBV infection is absent while *MYC* is translocated in all cases.
283 Moreover, although there are differences in the prevalence of some genetic alterations and gene
284 expression pattern, there are not differential molecular markers in the mutational landscape
285 between EBV⁺ and EBV⁻ lymphomas, including mutations in the *MYC* gene [15, 21, 59-61].
286 Second, more than 95% of the human adult population has been infected by EBV, but oncogenic
287 events related with EBV infection have a very low incidence, and actually the prevalence of EBV-
288 positive BL is decreasing [24]. Third, *MYC* translocation is not found in other tumors associated
289 with EBV infection, remarkably nasopharyngeal cancer, gastric cancer and Hodgkin lymphoma
290 [62-64]. Fourth, the EBV genes required for B cell transformation into lymphoblastoid cell lines
291 are not expressed in BL. Indeed, only the latent EBNA1 protein is consistently expressed in BL
292 and is unable to transform B cells. Moreover, *MYC* represses the EBV transforming LMP1 gene
293 [65]. It has been reported that EBNA2 and EBNA3C induce *MYC* expression [66-68], and that
294 EBNA3C induces AID, which could generate chromosomal translocations involving *MYC* [18, 19,
295 69]. EBV could induce other genetic changes in EBV-infected B cells [61]. However, neither
296 EBNA2 nor EBNA3C are expressed in BL.

297 Here we have shown that *CR2* is a *MYC* target gene and that *MYC* knockdown results in
298 decreased EBV infection, whereas *MYC* overexpression results in increased infection. A limitation
299 of our study is that our data are generated with human BL cell lines, not primary human B cells.
300 However, it is tempting to speculate that, at least in a relevant fraction of endemic BL cases, *MYC*
301 dysregulation occurs first, facilitating subsequent EVB infection. It must be noted that our results
302 do not contradict the canonical hypothesis (“virus first”) for BL development. Rather, they are
303 consistent with an alternative (but not mutually exclusive), “*MYC* first” mechanism that would be
304 at least partially responsible for the correlation between endemic BL and EBV infection. Both
305 hypotheses are depicted in Fig. 8. In accordance with the “*MYC* first” hypothesis, those B cells
306 with high *MYC* levels (due to translocation) would show an increased density of *CR2* receptors,
307 thus augmenting the probability of EBV infection. In agreement with previous reports [40] we have
308 detected in our Raji model that *MYC* knockdown activates EBV lytic genes. Therefore, *MYC* would
309 enhance viral infection on one hand but prevent the lytic cycle of infected cells on the other hand.
310 The “*MYC* first” mechanism would be compatible with the epidemiological data and the viral
311 clonality data, as the subsequent EBV infection will co-adjuvate to lymphoma development
312 through demonstrated mechanisms such as inhibition of apoptosis and evasion of the immune
313 surveillance, thus favoring the selection of *MYC*-expressing and EBV-infected cell clones. In
314 conclusion, our results showing that *CR2* is a direct *MYC* target gene provide new insights into
315 the understanding of BL. Further research should be undertaken to investigate the potential of
316 *CR2* regulation by *MYC* as a new therapeutic approach for BL treatment.

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318
319

320 **Methods**

321 **Extended Methods are included in the Supplementary Information**

322 **Cell culture and proliferation**

323 Raji, Jurkat, Ramos, K562, KMyCJ, KMER4, Kp27MER and B95-8 were grown in RPMI-1640 and
324 HeLa, HEK293T in DMEM both with 10% FBS and antibiotics. Viable cells were counted in
325 hemocytometer with Trypan Blue or in a Guava cell counter (Millipore).

326

327 **Cell cycle and apoptosis**

328 For cell cycle, cells were washed once with PBS, stained with Hoechst and analyzed by flow
329 cytometry. Apoptosis was assayed with the Annexin V-PE apoptosis detection kit (Immunostep).

330

331 **RNA and DNA extraction and quantification**

332 RNA extraction was performed using TriReagent (Sigma-Aldrich). Reverse transcription was
333 performed using the iScript cDNA Synthesis Kit (Bio-Rad). For EBV lytic genes, RNAs were
334 treated with DNase I (Invitrogen) prior to cDNA synthesis. gDNA was extracted with Qiagen
335 DNeasy Blood & Tissue kit. qPCRs were performed using 2xSYBR Select Master mix (Applied
336 Biosystem).

337

338 **Immunoblots**

339 Cells were lysed in 1% NP40 lysis buffer [70]. Protein extracts were sonicated and further clarified
340 by centrifugation. Samples were resolved by SDS-PAGE and transferred to a nitrocellulose
341 membrane. Signals were recorded with an Odyssey Infrared Imaging Scanner (LiCor
342 Biosciences).

343

344 **Transfection and luciferase assays**

345 Luciferase vectors were transfected using Amaxa Nucleofector for Raji and K562 cells. HEK293T
346 cells were transfected using PEI (Polysciences, Inc). Dual-Luciferase Reporter Assay System
347 (Promega) was used.

348

349 **Retroviral constructs**

350 The AID sequences were removed from the pMXPIE-AID retroviral vector [71] and the resulting
351 backbone was linked to the orange fluorescent protein gene mOrange2 generating the empty
352 plasmid pMX-IRES-mOrange2 further used to generate a pMX-MYC-IRES-mOrange2.

353

354 **Lentivirus and retrovirus production**

355 For lentivirus production, HEK293T cells were transfected with PEI with the lentiviral packaging
356 plasmids and the construct of interest. Supernatants were concentrated with PEG8000. Retroviral
357 supernatants were produced by transient calcium phosphate transfection of NIH-293T cells with
358 pCL-ECO (Novus) and pMX-Orange or pMX-MYC-Orange retroviral constructs.

359 **Flow cytometry and retroviral infection of mouse primary B cells**

360 Single cell suspensions from spleens were placed in culture and the mature B lymphocytes were
361 activated with LPS and IL4, and stained with antibodies. Mouse primary B cells were purified from
362 spleens of 4 months old C57/BL6 mice by anti-CD43, cultured for 24 h and transduced with control
363 pMX-Orange or pMX-MYC-Orange retrovirus. CD21 expression was analyzed by flow cytometry
364 in Orange-positive transduced cells.

365

366 **Chromatin immunoprecipitation**

367 Cells were fixed with 1% formaldehyde. After lysis, chromatin was sheared to 1000-500bp
368 fragments using a Bioruptor Plus Sonicator. 2-3 µg of antibody were added to diluted extracts and
369 incubated at 4°C overnight rotating. Immunoprecipitated material was purified with Dynabeads
370 Protein G (Invitrogen). Samples were eluted and des-crosslinked. DNA was purified with Qiaquick
371 PCR purification kit (Qiagen)

372

373 **Immunofluorescence**

374 Slides of Raji cells were obtained using a Cytospin, fixed with 4%PFA and blocked with 1%BSA-
375 PBS. For double immunofluorescence, samples were permeabilized with Triton X-100 before
376 blocking. Primary antibodies were incubated for 2 h, RT, washed with PBS and incubated with
377 secondary antibodies for 1 h at RT. Hoechst 3342 was used to stain nuclei. ImageJ software was
378 used for analysis and quantification.

379

380 **EBV production**

381 B95-8 cells were grown to saturation in 20%FBS-RPMI. After 3 weeks, EBV-containing
382 supernatants were collected and stored at -80°C. For short-term infections, EBV were
383 concentrated (20X) with 10% PEG8000.

384

385 **Statistical analyses**

386 Significance was determined by Student's two-tailed one-sample T test unless otherwise
387 specified. The Saphiro-Wilk normality test was applied to check normal distributions.

388

389

390 **Acknowledgements and Funding**

391 The work was supported by grants PID2020-115903GB-I00 to J.L and M.D.D., RTI2018-095673-
392 B-I00 to J.R.R., PID2019-107551RB-I00 to V.G-Y., PID2020-119567RB-I00 to R.M, PID2020-
393 117539GB-I00 to I.V. and PID2019-106773RB-I00 to A.R.R, all funded by
394 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/, Spanish Government, and by "FEDER, Una manera de
395 hacer Europa", European Union, and by La Caixa HR17-0244 grant to A.R. L.Q. and V.J. were
396 recipients of F.P.U. program and Universidad de Cantabria fellowships, respectively. L.G.G. was
397 a fellow of the Maria Zambrano program, Spanish Government. We are grateful to Maria
398 Aramburu and Patricia Arribas for technical help and Victor Campa por assistance in microscopy
399 and image processing.

400

401

402 **Conflict-of-interest disclosure:** The authors declare no competing financial interests

403

404 **Author contributions:**

405 E. M, L.G-G: formal analysis, investigation, writing. V.J., M. P-O, V.G.Y., R.B., A.V.M., J.C.A.
406 and, L.Q: formal analysis, investigation, resources. D.U., R.M., J.R.R. and I.V, formal analysis
407 and resources. I.M.A., A.R., formal analysis, resources, editing. M.D.D. formal analysis, funding,
408 writing. J.L., experimental design, formal analysis, writing, funding acquisition

409

410 **References**

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Down-regulation of MYC results in lower CR2 expression. **A** mRNA expression of *MYC* and *CR2* in Raji and Jurkat cells treated with JQ1 at the indicated concentrations for 6 and 12 h. The expression was determined by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3) * $P < 0.05$; *** $P < 0.005$ (with respect to non-treated cells). **B** Immunoblot showing the protein levels of MYC, CR2 and cyclin A in Raji and Jurkat cells treated with 1 μ M JQ1 for 24 h. β -Actin levels were used as loading control. **C** MYC and CR2 mRNA (left panel) and protein (right panel) levels assayed by RT-qPCR and immunoblot, respectively, from Raji cells transduced with either shMYC-containing lentiviral particles or empty vector (EV) control and selected with puromycin. β -Actin levels were used as loading control. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3). *** $P < 0.005$. **D** Proliferation of Raji cells transduced with either shMYC or EV control lentiviral particles measured by cell count after puromycin selection for 48 h. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n=3), normalized to cell counting at the start of the experiment. ** $P < 0.01$ by two tailed unpaired T-Test.

Figure 2. MYC induces CR2 expression in arrested cells. **A** Immunoblot showing MYC protein levels of KMyCJ cells treated with 75 μ M ZnSO₄ and 1 μ M JQ1 for 24 h. β -Actin levels were used as loading control. **B** Proliferation of KMyCJ cells treated with 75 μ M ZnSO₄ and/or 1 μ M JQ1 for 48 h, measured by cell counting and normalized to untreated cells. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n=4) * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.005$. **C** Upper graph: scheme of the conditional MYC expression by ZnSO₄ and repression by JQ1 in KMyCJ cells. Lower graph: *MYC* and *CR2* mRNA levels in KMyCJ cells treated with 75 μ M ZnSO₄ and/or 1 μ M JQ1 for 24 h determined by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n=3). ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.005$. **D** Proliferation of KMyCJ cells treated with 75 μ M ZnSO₄ and/or 10 nM TPA for 48 h, measured by cell counting and normalized to untreated cells. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n = 3). *** $P < 0.005$. **E** Upper graph: scheme of the conditional MYC expression by 75 μ M ZnSO₄ and repression by 10 nM TPA in KMyCJ cells. Lower graph: *MYC* and *CR2* expression levels in KMyCJ cells treated with ZnSO₄ and/or TPA for 48 h determined by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n=3) * $P < 0.05$; *** $P < 0.005$. **F** Proliferation of Kp27MER cells treated with 200 nM 4HT and/or 75 μ M ZnSO₄ for 48 h, measured by cell counting and normalized to untreated cells. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n = 4). ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.005$. **G** Upper graph: scheme of the conditional MYC activation by 4HT and p27 induction by ZnSO₄ in Kp27MER cells. Lower graph: *CR2*, *LDHA* and *p27/CDKN1B* expression from Kp27MER treated with ZnSO₄ and 4HT for 24 h determined by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n=3); * $P < 0.05$ by two-tailed unpaired t-test.

Figure 3. Binding of MYC to the promoter of CR2. **A** Schematic representation of *CR2* chromosome localization and MYC and MAX binding sites according with ChIP-seq data of the ENCODE project (UCSC Genome Browser, GRCh37/hg19 release) in EBV-transformed human B cells (GM12878 cell line). TBP (TATA-box binding protein) is also shown to mark the transcription initiation complex binding. **B** Schematic representation of *CR2* proximal promoter

and the first exon and intron. The horizontal bars represent the regions amplified by the different primers used in the ChIP analysis. **C** ChIP with anti-MYC antibody on *CR2* gene of Raji cells. Exon9 (+19.6 Kb) of *CR2* gene was used as negative control and a *LDHA* proximal promoter region mapping -85 bp to +19 bp was used as positive control for MYC binding. Non-specific IgG was used to normalize the data. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n=3). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.005$ determined by two tail unpaired T-Test. **D** *CR2* promoter activity measured by luciferase assay of Raji cells transfected with a *CR2* promoter luciferase reporter and transduced with shMYC-containing lentiviral particles (or the corresponding empty vector, EV). Luciferase activity was determined 48 h after infection. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n=3). * $P < 0.05$. **E** MYC occupancy on *CR2* promoter assayed by ChIP using an anti-MYC antibody in 293T cells transfected with the luciferase constructs containing either wild type (Wt) or mutated E-box1 or E-box2 *CR2* promoter. The binding of MYC was analysed on an amplicon (blue line) comprising sequences of *CR2* promoter and of the luciferase ORF. Non-specific IgG was used as negative control and data normalised with respect to the binding of MYC to the wild type promoter construct. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3) ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.005$.

Figure 4. CR2 is a direct MYC target gene. A Scheme showing the two possible mechanisms from MYC-mediated induction of *CR2* expression. Left: the direct cycloheximide insensitive mechanism. Right: the indirect cycloheximide sensitive mechanism by which MYC would induce another transcription factor (TF) which in turn would activate *CR2* expression. **B** MYC and MYC-ER protein levels from KMER4 cells treated with 200 nM 4HT and 50 μ g/mL cycloheximide (CHX). After 6 h of treatment, cell lysates were prepared and analyzed by immunoblot. β -Actin levels were used as loading control. **C** Upper graph: scheme of the conditional MYC activation by 4HT and effect of cycloheximide (CHX) in KMER4 cells. Lower graph: expression of *CR2* mRNA in KMER4 cells treated with 4HT and CHX. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3). * $P < 0.05$; *** $P < 0.005$.

Figure 5. Myc induces CR2 expression in primary B cells. A Cell surface CR2/CD21 levels in splenic mouse B cells with the 10% highest MYC expression levels (dark grey) as compared to the rest of the cells (light grey). B cells were prepared from 18 weeks old C57/BL6 wild type mice analyzed by flow cytometry. Two representative overlay histograms are shown at the left and quantification of CR2 mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) at the right. Data are mean values \pm S.D. (n = 6) *** $P < 0.005$. **B** Mature B lymphocytes from the spleens of *Myc^{flox/flox};Max^{flox/+};cd19^{cre/+};Rosa26^{gfp/gfp}* (MycKO, n=3) homozygous and *Myc^{flox/+};Max^{flox/+};Cd19^{cre/+};Rosa26^{gfp/gfp}* heterozygous control (n = 3) mice were activated with LPS and IL-4 for 48h. Cells were stained with the indicated antibodies and analysed by flow cytometry. GFP⁺ cells (*Myc* deleted B lymphocytes) were gated and surface expression of CR2/CD21 was analysed. Absolute numbers of CR2^{hi} are shown. n = 3, *** $P < 0.005$. by two-tailed unpaired t test. **C** Left panel, upper graph: schematic representation of the pMX-MYC-IRES-Orange retroviral vector used in the experiments. MMLV: LTR and ψ sequences of MMLV virus; Puro and

Amp, puromycin and ampicillin resistance genes. Right panel, bottom graph: expression of CR2 in mouse splenic B cells after MYC overexpression. CD43⁻ B cells isolated from spleens were cultured with LPS and interleukin-4 for 24h and transduced with pMX-MYC-Orange retrovirus and the control retrovirus (EV) during 48 h. CR2 was assayed in Orange⁺ transduced cells. Two representative overlay histograms are shown at the left and quantification of CR2 mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) at the right. Data are mean values \pm S.D., $n = 5$, * $P < 0.05$ by two-tailed unpaired t test.

Figure 6. MYC depletion decreases EBV infection of B cells. **A** gDNA levels of LMP1 and EBNA1 viral genes from Raji and Ramos cells analyzed by PCR. Data normalized against *LDHA* and *CR2* gDNA levels (same genomic regions used in ChIP experiments (Supplementary Table 1)). **B** Depletion of MYC protein assessed by immunoblot after lentiviral transduction with two short-hairpin MYC constructs in Ramos cells. Subsequent experiments were performed using a mixture of the two shRNA. **C** *MYC* and *CR2* mRNA levels from Ramos cells transduced with lentiviral particles expressing shMYC and empty vector (EV) followed by 3 days of EBV infection and analyzed by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). * $P < 0.05$. **D** Scheme of the experiment. **E** *EBNA1* and *LMP1* gDNA levels in Ramos cells infected with EBV, quantified by qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. ($n = 3$) *** $P < 0.005$. **F** Scheme of the experiment. **G** *MYC* mRNA levels from Raji cells transduced with lentiviral particles expressing shMYC or empty vector (EV), analyzed by RT-qPCR after 3 days of puromycin selection. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). *** $P < 0.005$. **H** Levels of the EBV envelope protein gp350/250 in control cells (EV) and MYC knock down (shMYC) cells after 2.5 h of EBV infection. The gp350/250 area was normalized to the nuclei area. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. ($n = 3$) *** $P < 0.05$. Right panel: representative field showing the gp350/250 (green) and nuclei stained with Hoechst 33342 (blue).

Figure 7. MYC overexpression increases EBV infection of B cells. **A** Scheme of the experiment in B. **B** Immunoblot showing the levels of MYC in cells transduced with lentivirus expressing MYC and the empty vector (EV) followed by 48 h of EBV infection. β -Actin was used as loading control. **C** *EBNA1* and *LMP1* gDNA levels in Ramos cells transduced with MYC lentivirus and EBV, quantified by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). * $P < 0.05$.

Figure 8. Two non-mutually exclusive models for pathogenesis of Burkitt lymphoma. In the “classical” model, EBV infection occurs first and promotes MYC translocation. The results presented here allow the proposal of a second model by which MYC translocation in tumor initiating cells leads to overexpression CR2, thus facilitating EBV infection. Created with BioRender.com.

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A

B

C

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CLASSICAL MODEL: virus first

ALTERNATIVE MODEL: MYC first